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ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS’ CREATIVE ABILITIES

Abstract. This article is devoted to the organizational and pedagogical conditions for the development of students' creative abilities in secondary schools, covering the issues of increasing the level of students' competence, educating students with creative competence, and organizing classes aimed at developing students' creativity. Attention is also paid to the conditions and pedagogical foundations for developing the creativity of subject teachers.

Keywords: students, pedagogical conditions, traditional education, modern technologies, creativity, initiative, creative teaching, innovative education, teacher activity.

In the 21st century, education is recognized as a key factor in ensuring sustainable development worldwide, and the new education concept set for 2030 includes the process of “Creating opportunities for quality education throughout life” as one of the urgent tasks. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5712 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” [1] of April 29, 2019 approved this decree. In this decree, the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System until 2030 pays special attention to further improving teaching methodologies, gradually implementing the principles of individualization in educational processes, introducing modern information, communication and innovative technologies into the education system, and thereby increasing the creative abilities and level of competence of students.

As we know, the future of every society is determined by the level of

development of its education system, which is its integral part and vital necessity. Today, in our country, which is moving along the path of independent development, the reform and improvement of the continuous education system, its elevation to a new qualitative level, and the increase in the efficiency of education have risen to the level of state policy. With the adoption of the new edition of the Law “On Education” [2], the basis for the training of modern personnel through the continuous education system has also been improved.

Until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge. This method stifled independent thinking, creative research, and initiative in students. Nowadays, interest and attention to increasing the effectiveness of education using the most advanced educational technologies in the educational process is growing day by day. Classes using modern technologies are aimed at helping students search for the knowledge they are acquiring, independently study and analyze it, draw conclusions on their own, and develop their creativity.

The main goal of creative education of students in secondary schools is to develop students' creative competence and effectively organize their creative activities.

Increasing the level of students' competence is important in developing their creativity.

Students with creative competence demonstrate the following:

- can deeply understand the content and essence of the tasks given by the teacher;
- actively participates in innovative learning environments;
- can use opportunities for self-expression;
- learning and cognitive activities are effective;
- can independently use electronic learning tools;

- can use creativity in classes;
- can apply the acquired knowledge in practice;
- develops new ideas;
- expresses ideas that no one else has ever thought of;
- asks unusual questions;
- enjoys solving problems that have no solution;
- sometimes expresses ideas that are not related to the topic;
- has the ability to work independently;
- can create new projects;

Researchers identify the following main tasks aimed at the formation of professional competence in teachers [3]:

1. Creating an educational environment that promotes maximum personal development.
2. Improving curricula aimed at developing creativity
3. Instilling educational and cognitive activity.
4. Forming self-education skills.

It is advisable to conduct lessons organized in general education schools to develop students' creativity based on the following conditions:

1. Forming motivation for learning in students;
2. Self-control and management;
3. Introducing innovative, pedagogical technologies into educational processes;
4. Creating a creative learning environment and applying creative and interactive methods to it;

Let us explain each of these requirements:

Motivation is the emergence of students' desire for educational and cognitive activities. If motivation is not formed in students, it becomes somewhat more difficult to achieve educational effectiveness. It is precisely the formation of

motivation that leads to the development of creative activity in students. Only then will students' self-confidence increase, they will strive to create new ideas.

Self-control and management - In educational processes, it is important for teachers and students to manage their own activities. This leads to the emergence of reflection in students.

The introduction of innovative, pedagogical technologies in educational processes - creates a basis for students to acquire knowledge in the subject not in a ready-made form, but through their independent research. Innovative technologies help students broaden their horizons, master the secrets of science, retain the information they have received in their memory for a long time, and form a culture of teamwork.

Creating a creative learning environment and applying creative and interactive methods to it - creative learning develops students' ability to create new, original ideas in any activity. Interactive methods (English: Inter-mutual, collaborative, action) help students develop their collaborative skills. In this case, by dividing students into small groups and teams, they effectively develop their communication skills, respect for their peers' opinions, and the ability to listen.

We have witnessed that some of the reviewed research studies were conducted in the direction of providing pedagogical conditions to increase students' creativity and using various modern methods and technologies for creative development.

In particular, the textbook “Creative Pedagogy and Psychology” by A.V. Morozov and D.V. Chernilevsky [4] analyzes the process of preparing future specialists for pedagogical activity in higher education. It examines the motivation for learning, education and creativity, creativity and its description, methods of solving creative problems, an analysis of questions related to an important element of creative pedagogy and psychology using the example of didactic games.

Yu.R. Varlakova also describes the creative ability of bachelors studying in the

field of pedagogy in her research work as the ability to quickly develop ideas aimed at non-standard and functional goals in order to achieve creative results in their future professional activities, based on self-awareness, knowledge in the field of pedagogy [5].

He describes several conditions for developing teachers' creativity:

- activities that organize the educational process, teaching in groups using interactive methods and based on situational problems;

- activities outside the educational process, participation of students in various competitions and exhibitions.

In the research work of A.S. Makarova, one can see the main tools for developing creativity. These are:

- having a creative character;

- using ICT;

- creating reality in connection with practice;

- developing problematic questions [6].

Ye.Ye. Shcherbakova also characterizes pedagogical creativity in her research based on the analysis of the content of communicative and didactic creativity and distinguishes several indicators of creative abilities [7]:

- ingenuity;

- the ability to combine;

- divergent (separate) thinking;

- visual creativity;

- associative abilities.

The scientific research of Uzbek pedagogical scientists O.Musurmanova [8], Sh.Sharipov [9], N.Egamberdieva [10] and others shed light on the specific aspects of developing creative abilities in students in the formation of professional and innovative readiness of future specialists, social factors influencing the development

of creative qualities, ways and forms of increasing personal activity, developing critical and creative thinking in students, its existing pedagogical conditions, didactic support, and the content of pedagogical creativity.

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